

WHAT IS REINCARNATE

Reincarnate aims at advancing circular economy practices within the European construction industry and enabling to significantly maximise the life cycle of buildings, construction products and materials, reduce CDW by 80%, increase the reusability of buildings, construction products and materials and, as a result, lower the sector's emissions by 70%.

Figure 1. Positioned moisture measurement sensor at the support point in Pankow

CONTEXT AND INNOVATION

The condition assessment and maintenance of existing timber structures remain a key challenge in the transition towards a circular built environment. Timber roof trusses, in particular, are highly sensitive to environmental conditions such as moisture and temperature, which can lead to progressive degradation and reduced structural performance over time. Traditional inspection methods are often limited to visual assessments, which may fail to detect early-stage damage or capture temporal variations in material behaviour.

This work addresses these limitations through the application of non-destructive testing (NDT) methods combined with continuous sensor-based monitoring. Manual inspection techniques are complemented with environmental and material measurements, enabling a more accurate and data-driven evaluation of structural condition. The study focuses on identifying moisture-related degradation mechanisms and understanding their evolution through in-situ monitoring in real-world case studies.

Aligned with the REINCARNATE innovations “Building Inspection & Valuation” and “Predictive Life-Cycle Information”, the proposed approach contributes to improving the reliability of condition assessment and establishing a foundation for predictive lifecycle analysis. The results support the development of monitoring-based strategies for maintenance, life extension, and more informed decision-making in the management of existing building components.

DEMONSTRATION AND RESULTS

The proposed approach was implemented through two real-world case studies involving timber roof structures located in Werdau and Berlin-Pankow. In both cases, the methodology combined manual inspection with sensor-based monitoring to assess structural condition under varying environmental influences. Measurements focused on key parameters such as timber moisture content, temperature, and relative humidity, providing a detailed representation of the conditions affecting material performance.

Figure 2. Structural Health Monitoring Platform from sensor provider

Data was collected using installed sensors that continuously monitored environmental and material conditions over time. This allowed the identification of correlations between moisture levels and potential degradation risks, particularly in structurally sensitive areas. The monitoring setup enabled the observation of temporal variations that are not accessible through conventional inspection methods.

The results demonstrate that continuous monitoring significantly enhances the understanding of timber behaviour under real conditions and improves the detection of moisture-related risks. The combination of in-situ measurements and inspection data provides a more reliable basis for assessing structural condition. These findings support the use of NDT-based monitoring as a foundation for future predictive lifecycle assessment approaches.

Figure 3. Samples of temperature and moisture content readings

TECHNICAL HIGHLIGHTS

- › Application of non-destructive testing methods for timber condition assessment
- › Continuous monitoring of moisture content, temperature, and relative humidity
- › Integration of manual inspection and sensor-based data collection
- › Identification of moisture-related degradation risks in timber structures
- › Observation of temporal changes in environmental and material conditions

REPLICATION POTENTIAL

The approach is transferable to timber structures where environmental conditions drive degradation. Its application depends on sensor availability, access to structures, and engineering expertise. Integration into digital systems such as CP-IM would require standardised data formats and interoperability.

IMPACTS AND REPLICATION

CATEGORY	FOCUS	CONTRIBUTION LEVEL
Scientific	Supports data-driven condition assessment and predictive lifecycle modelling.	High
Societal	Contributes to safer structures and extended service life.	Medium
Techno-economic	Improves inspection workflows without full industrial validation.	Medium

LINKS

<https://www.reincarnate-project.eu/>

CONTACTS

Demo Case Owner

TU Berlin

Innovation Owner

DMO, TUB